

Modelling and strategies for the assessment and **Optimisation**
of **Energy Usage** aspects of rail innovation

Deliverable Report

Document identifier: **OPEUS D8.1**

Date Due to EC: **Month 1 – November 2016**

Date of Delivery to EC: **20/09/2017**

Deliverable Title: **Dissemination Plan**

Dissemination level: **PU**

Work Package: **WP8**

Lead Beneficiary: **UNEW**

Other beneficiaries involved: **SAFT, UIC, UITP, UROS, STAV**

Document Status: Final

Document Link: ~

The OPEUS project consortium consists of:

No	Name	Short name	Country
1	Newcastle University	UNEW	UK
2	SAFT SAS	SAFT	FR
3	Union Internationale des Chemin de Fer	UIC	FR
4	Union Internationale des Transport Public	UITP	BE
5	Universitaet Rostock	UROS	DE
6	Stadler Rail Valencia SAU	STAV	ES

Document History:

Version	Date	Modification Reason	Modified by
Draft 1	Nov 2016	Document Initiated	Belinda Fairbairn, UNEW
Draft 2	July 2017	Content updated and developed	Belinda Fairbairn, UNEW Roberto Palacin, UNEW
Draft 3	8 th August 2017	Content updated and developed. Issued to OPEUS consortium for final comment / agreement	Belinda Fairbairn, UNEW
Draft 4	12 th September 2017	Partner comments and feedback combined	Daria Kuzmina, UITP Isabelle De Keyzer, UIC Belinda Fairbairn, UNEW
Draft 5	19 th September 2017	Content developed to address feedback and comments	Belinda Fairbairn, UNEW
Final	20 th September 2017	Document checked and issued	Belinda Fairbairn, UNEW

Disclaimer

This report was prepared as an account of work funded by Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking. The contents of this document are provided "as is", and no guarantee or warranty is provided that the information is fit for particular purposes. The information, analyses and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the Community institutions and bodies, nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein. The user, thereof, uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

Copyright notice

© 2016 – 2019 OPEUS Consortium

Table of Contents:

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
INTRODUCTION	5
DISSEMINATION OBJECTIVES	5
TARGET AUDIENCE	5
PROJECT IDENTITY	6
COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	7
Internal project communications.....	7
Website.....	8
Use of partners' existing communication channels.....	8
Social media.....	9
Coordination with complementary project FINE1.....	9
Publications.....	9
External events.....	10
OPEUS events.....	11
IPR AND RELATED ISSUES	11
ADVISORY BOARD AND DISSEMINATION	12
TRACKING AND REPORTING DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	12
CONCLUSIONS	14
ANNEX 1	15
Examples of OPEUS project document templates.....	15

Table of Figures:

Figure 1: a) OPEUS project logo and b) appropriate funders' disclaimers.....	7
Figure 2: OPEUS Project extranet structure.....	8
Figure 3: OPEUS template for Partners' reporting of dissemination activity.....	13
Figure 4: OPEUS template for Partners' reporting of scientific publications.....	13

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report defines the Dissemination Plan, comprising Deliverable 8.1, for the OPEUS project and describes the materials and strategies that will be used to facilitate the wide-spread of information and knowledge of the results created by the project.

The Plan was developed in association with UIC as the lead for WP8 "Engagement" and all WP Partners in line with the project's Description of Action (DoA) as approved by the European Commission. It reinforces the Terms and Conditions relating to Dissemination in "Grant Agreement number: 730827 — OPEUS". The dissemination of OPEUS will be carried out with the cooperation of all Work Packages.

Once the context of the OPEUS project and WP8 "Engagement" has been introduced, this report highlights the components of a Dissemination Plan covering internal and external activities, aimed at raising awareness of the project and to encourage industry participation in its practical aspects. These include, the creation of a project identity and website, definition of the target audience, communication channels to be used, publication of results in various media including OPEUS's involvement in the H2020 Open Research Data pilot, the organization of dissemination events, the participation to external events, and the contributions of an Advisory Board. We also touch upon the importance of recognising IPR and related issues and confirm how OPEUS will organise the reporting of dissemination activities to the Shift2Rail JU and EC.

The OPEUS project Management Board (MB) (i.e. representatives from the project coordinator and all Work Package leads) will monitor the delivery of this Plan throughout the project lifetime. The MB will advise upon, and contribute towards, the Plan's continued development, as it is expected that it may require revisiting and updating to continue the dissemination effort, in light of emerging project results.

INTRODUCTION

Within the scope of the OPEUS project, the focus of Work Package 8 (WP8) is “Engagement”. Its objective is “to establish a clear and fruitful communication platform between the OPEUS activities and those outside the consortium focusing in particular on the essential relationship with the Shift2Rail (S2R) founding members and associates and their innovation activities related to OPEUS”.

WP8 runs throughout the project’s 30-month duration. This Deliverable 8.1 “Dissemination Plan” takes into account the Tasks of WP8, whilst reflecting the requirements of “Article 29 - Dissemination of Results - Open Access - Visibility of Funding” as required in the Terms and Conditions of “Grant Agreement number: 730827 — OPEUS”.

DISSEMINATION OBJECTIVES

It was agreed at OPEUS’ proposal stage that the content of the Plan would detail some specific actions, as a minimum, including:

- The project identity
- Communication channels
- Publications
- External events
- OPEUS events
- IPR and related issues

TARGET AUDIENCE

This Plan has been formulated to be consistent with the OPEUS project’s Description of Action (DoA) objectives. It has been designed to be flexible, capable of responding to the needs of the project as the activity is undertaken. The strategic aim of OPEUS dissemination is to increase the visibility of the research and innovation work to be undertaken and to engage actors from beyond the project consortium by establishing suitable dialogue and cooperation with them, specifically:

- The S2R Joint Undertaking (JU) management and key founding and associate members working towards innovations relevant to energy

optimisation in the different Technology Demonstrators (TDs), as specified in Innovation Programmes (IPs). This will include links with the FINE1 project consortium addressing complementary topic *S2R-CFM-CCA-02-2015 – “Energy and sustainability, including noise and vibrations baseline assessment”*

- Urban and main line operators that will become the end users of the OPEUS tool and that can contribute to the development of enhanced duty cycles through their representative organisations i.e. UITP and UIC
- Policy makers (both public transport authority and local authority) that can benefit from the outline view of urban rail systems energy requirements and the global vision of energy usage in railways.
- Passenger transport industry and manufacturers, research centres and institutions, and passenger transport users

PROJECT IDENTITY

Including its own logo, a cohesive visual identity has been created for use by the OPEUS project Partners, e.g. documents, reports, presentations and other external communications. Examples of this visual identity, are included at Annex 1 (this Deliverable Report is, itself, an example).

The use of the JU logo, EC emblem and wording “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730827” will be used by all project Partners where appropriate, but certainly on all dissemination of results in the frame of the OPEUS project, unless the JU requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible¹.

In similar vein, any activity involving the dissemination of results will indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.²

These logos and appropriate associated wording are shown in Figure 1, below:

¹ Grant Agreement, Article 29.4: Information on funding — Obligation and right to use the JU logo and the EU emblem.

² Grant Agreement Article 29.5: Disclaimer excluding JU responsibility.

Figure 1: a) OPEUS project logo and b) appropriate funders' disclaimers

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Given the relatively small size of the project and its focused nature, communication channels will align where possible with existing channels, for example:

Internal project communications

For internal project communications, WP8 lead UIC has created a workspace for OPEUS on their Extranet facility, to enable all project partners to access share documents and reports, develop WP delivery activities, etc. Figure 2, below, depicts the file structure currently within the extranet. This will adapt and be amended to suit the project and partners' requirements as delivery occurs:

UIC EXTRANET
Belinda FAIRBAIRN - Tuesday 19 September 2017

Home Logout Workspaces User's menu Guides Search

Folders Upload Trash

File manager

OPEUS : .../OPEUS

Posted by	Name	Description	Modified	Version	Modified by	Size	Hits
	1-Communication with the EU						
	2-Steering board						
	3-Common documents						
	4-Deliverables						
	5-Interim Reporting M1-M8						
	WP1 Urban rail systems energy requirements						
	WP2 Simulation model and tool development						
	WP3 Reference scenario simulations						
	WP4 DAS study						
	WP5 In-vehicle energy losses study						
	WP6 Advanced Energy Storage Systems (ESSs) Study						
	WP7 Global Vision						
	WP8 Engagement						
	WP9 Management						
FAIRBAIRN Belinda	OPEUS Consortium contacts 010817.pdf	OPEUS Consortium Contacts, 1-8-2017	2017-08-02 17:03		FAIRBAIRN Belinda	78 kb	2

UIC Membership | List of UIC members | UIC Projects | UIC Website | Terms and conditions | Contact | Top of Page |

© photo credit: RZD, Fotolia, ÖBB, Railinfra Opleidingen, TCDD, HZ Holding, RAI, UIC

Webmaster - Powered by Ovidentia
Ovidentia™ is a registered trademark of Cantico.

Figure 2: OPEUS Project extranet structure (as at the time of writing)

Website

A basic, simple and standard website has been created (www.opeus-project.eu) by UIC and linked to the S2R main website, as well the websites of other OPEUS partners as appropriate. The OPEUS website includes an area where project Deliverable Reports classified as "PU" in the DoA can be made available for public download, once they have been approved by the Shift2Rail JU / European Commission

Use of partners' existing communication channels

The already existing and effective communications and dissemination channels of the partners involved will be used, for example, electronic newsletters including news of the project launch, OPEUS website, interim progress reports, meetings of various appropriate working groups e.g. those of UITP and UIC, etc.

Social media

The development of a standard social media presence will be investigated to assess if it could be appropriate, e.g. LinkedIn, to communicate relevant outcomes particularly on the tasks related to the global vision of energy usage in railway systems as well as the dissemination of published results for maximum impact

Coordination with complementary project FINE1

Particular emphasis will be made on coordinating the activities of OPEUS with those of relevant S2R projects and activities, primarily FINE1. A Collaboration Agreement between OPEUS and FINE1 has been established, to enable the regular interchange of information and experiences between the two projects. This will strengthen both projects' communication and dissemination potential and project impacts.

Publications

OPEUS results are expected to generate high quality scientific peer-reviewed publications (open access) reflecting the advances on the existing knowledge in areas such as simulation-based optimisation methodologies, energy usage of railway systems, quantification and evaluation of losses in the traction chain, role of innovative technologies in energy optimisation and development of DAS-aided strategies. Publications will be self-archived with 'green' open access and where possible published in open access journals that offer immediate free online access. If required, 'gold' access to selective peer reviewed publications will be followed to improve citations and discoverability.

To cover these cases, funds to pay the Article Processing Charge (APC) were added to the OPEUS proposal as a project-specific cost, although steps will be put in place to minimise such costs. For instance, Newcastle University is a leading member of ECTRI³, which would allow waiving the Gold Access fees to its peer-review journal *European Transport Research Review* published by Springer (<http://link.springer.com/journal/12544>), which aims to disseminate research results in the field of transport. Other key publications to be targeted include *Applied Energy* (<http://www.journals.elsevier.com/applied-energy/>) and the *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part F: Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit*.

³ European Conference of Transport Research Institutes www.ectri.org

The archiving and publications management systems of both Newcastle University and Rostock University are fully compliant with H2020 requirements for storage of research data. In addition, the UIC-managed database SPARK (www.sparkrail.org) will also be used for publication management and dissemination purposes as it will be the OpenAIRE database (www.openaire.eu). More general publications e.g. press releases and articles in trade press will also be pursued.

OPEUS will take part in the H2020 Open Research Data pilot. The dissemination and exploitation actions related to publications will contribute to the Data Management Plan (DMP) to be published by the coordinator on behalf of the consortium (Deliverable 9.3). This document will cover the following four key areas:

- *Data overview* - Description of the types of primary and secondary data to be collected, created or used. Particularly relevant will be the outline governing the use of open rather than proprietary file formats for long term storage
- *Standards and metadata* - Description of the metadata (i.e. data that describes the data standards) to be adopted. The guidance provided by the UK's Digital Curation Centre (www.dcc.ac.uk) will be followed
- *Data sharing* - Description of how the data will be shared e.g. persistent links (digital object identifier, DOI). A number of repositories have already been mentioned above (e.g. OpenAIRE)
- *Archiving and preservation* - Description on the strategy for data preservation including storage during the project's lifetime. For instance, Newcastle University's data will be stored on the central file storage service hosted across two data centres and operating a "shadow copies" approach (taken four times daily).

External events

Identification is ongoing of relevant external events where the OPEUS presence will be of added value for both the project and the event itself. These could include conferences, exhibitions, fairs and congresses which may present dissemination opportunities for OPEUS including delivery of presentations and industry networking.

Events with dissemination opportunities being considered to date include both large events e.g. TRA2018, UITP Global Public Transport Summit, and the World Congress on Rail Research 2019 (WCRR'19) as well as smaller, more focused ones e.g. UIC Energy-efficiency days, addressing a range of topics concerning energy use within the rail sector. A list of such external events including their dates and locations can be collated within the OPEUS extranet, for reference and discussion between project partners as the project timeline progresses, and will also be an important source of information to reference when reporting dissemination activity to the Commission. OPEUS will actively seek to engage and be involved in events organised by S2R and relevant projects on the energy subject.

OPEUS events

OPEUS will also organise its own events (e.g. through and with the Advisory Board) to engage with other stakeholders as well as provide specific training for S2R members in using the OPEUS tool to be developed as project delivery progresses.

Specifically, a Final Event will be scheduled by the project by Month 30, subject matter of Deliverable 8.3 by UIC. This final event will facilitate the presentation of the main outcomes of the project to external delegates.

IPR AND RELATED ISSUES

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) will be effectively managed to ensure the correct balance between disseminating information to the widest possible target audience and protecting each partners' IPR and associated commercial interests.

To assist in the exploitation and the implementation of the results, all OPEUS deliverables will be "Public". A consortium agreement based on the H2020 DESCA model was completed before the start of OPEUS, which includes the addressing of knowledge management and protection issues e.g.;

- background, and specific limitations and/or conditions for implementation (if any) and for exploitation
- results, regarding (joint) ownership and transfer of results
- access rights to background and results for implementation and exploitation purposes

- publications, procedures for dissemination of research results and related open access conditions.

ADVISORY BOARD AND DISSEMINATION

An Advisory Board (AB) has been set up for OPEUS as a key instrument to maximise project impact. It involves industry stakeholders and, in particular, S2R members with active interest in energy optimisation aspects from a variety of perspectives. It also includes a representative of the FINE1 project consortium addressing complementary topic *S2R-CFM-CCA-02-2015*. The members of the AB represent a spectrum of bodies, some of which are already participants in OPEUS e.g. UIC and UITP. The role of the OPEUS AB is:

- To act as a sounding board, provide advice, facilitate and improve the work being developed within the project feedback on approach and progress of the project
- To take the results and disseminate them further within their existing networks by opening up paths for engagement, dissemination, exploitation and adoption of the OPEUS results by the wider railway community and especially to feed into the innovation activities being carried out within the S2R framework.

The AB will be invited to attend specific full consortium meetings and alongside these there will be specific sessions for the OPEUS team to report progress achieved and discuss the project's next steps with the AB members. The AB will be chaired by Mr Bart Van der Spiegel of the Belgian infrastructure manager INFRABEL, and is envisaged to integrate outstanding international experts from Europe and beyond. The final constitution of the OPEUS AB is to be subject to S2R JU approval.

TRACKING AND REPORTING DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

As part of the reporting responsibilities within its H2020 Grant Agreement, the OPEUS project will compile a complete record of dissemination activities and also inform the Commission of the occurrences of scientific publications. An example of the OPEUS dissemination activities reporting template for all partners to use to report their dissemination activities is shown below in Figure 3;

Figure 3: OPEUS template for Partners' reporting of dissemination activity

Similarly, Figure 4 illustrates the template used by the project coordinator to gather information about scientific publications from Partners;

Figure 4: OPEUS template for Partners' reporting of scientific publications

UNEW will actively lobby OPEUS partners every 6-8 months to remind them to complete their responsibilities for reporting both dissemination and communication activities and occurrences of scientific publications. Information obtained from these ongoing actions will be included by UNEW to the Continuous Reporting tool within the EC Participant Portal Grant Management System, evidencing the project's effort applied to maximising engagement, dissemination and exploitation potential of OPEUS activity and results. In this way, that they will also be included to the formal 1st Periodic, 2nd Periodic and Final Project Reports.

CONCLUSIONS

This concise Dissemination Plan has been designed to maximise communication about the progress and impact of the OPEUS project. It has described the materials and strategies to be used for internal and external communication, engagement and uptake of the results by relevant stakeholders. Dissemination activities will be discussed and coordinated via WP8 "Engagement".

UIC, as WP8 lead, has secured the website domain name and the website itself is (at the time of finalising this report) developed and ready to launch. The website will be especially useful to advertise specific events at which OPEUS will be represented and/or will be hosting, this being updated by all Consortium members as appropriate throughout the project lifetime.

It is anticipated that more dissemination opportunities will arise as project delivery progresses therefore the Plan will be utilised by the OPEUS consortium and Advisory Board, over the lifetime of the project, to help to maximise the return for the time invested by project Partners and stakeholders in undertaking the various dissemination activities.

ANNEX 1

Examples of OPEUS project document templates

a) OPEUS Agenda template document:

Topic	Progress Meeting	
Venue	Research Beehive, Old Library Bldg, Newcastle University, NE1 7RU, UK	
Contact	Roberto Palacin [roberto.palacin@ncl.ac.uk] [+44 7976 906711_calls only]	

Agenda

Time	Activity	Who?
09.00-09.15	Welcome and introduction	
09.15-09.30		
09.30-10.30		
10.30-10.45	Coffee break	
10.45-11.30		
11.30-13.00		
13.00-14.00	Lunch	
13.45-14.15		
14.00-15.30		
15.30-17.00		
17.00	End of meeting	

The OPEUS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 730827

OPEUS_ WRnumber _Agenda Meeting Title_ Meeting Location & Date_ DocVersion_ PartnerName_

This report reflects only the author's view and the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

b) OPEUS Presentation template:

Click to add title

Click to add subtitle

The OPEUS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 730827

This report reflects only the author's view and the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Contact details

Coordinator **Roberto Palacin**
Newcastle University roberto.palacin@ncl.ac.uk

The OPEUS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 730827

This report reflects only the author's view and the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

c) OPEUS Minutes of Meeting template:

Project title: Modelling and strategies for the assessment and Optimisation of Energy Usage aspects of rail innovation
Project number: 730827

Minutes of the Meeting

Topic	Kick-Off Meeting, 4 th November 2016
Venue	ECTRL c/o POLIS, rue du Trône 98, 1050 Brussels
Contact	Roberto Palacin [roberto.palacin@ncl.ac.uk] [+44 7976 906711, satb only]

CONTENT

- Welcome and introduction of the participants
- Agenda items
- Annexes including Action Points

ANNEXES

- AGENDA
- ATTENDANCE LIST
- TO DO LIST

The meeting started at xx:xx [CC]

The OPEUS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 730827

This report reflects only the author's view and the EU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

The meeting closed at xx:xx

ANNEX 1- AGENDA

ANNEX 2- ATTENDANCE LIST

ANNEX 3: TO DO LIST

OPEUS_WBNumber_MoM Meeting Title _Meeting Location & Date _DocVersion _FactoName

